

EVALUATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN ROHILKHAND PLAINS : A GEOGRAPHICAL STUDY

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Abstract:-

The Upper Ganga River basin is socio-economically the most important river basin in India. Rohilkhand plains one of the major part of upper Ganga plains. In this region most of the peoples are dependent upon Agriculture which is the main source of their income. This region is characterized by its backwardness in terms of socio economic- conditions. Recently Socio-economic status in rural areas of Rohilkhand plains is gradually improving over a period of time.

Many policies have been implemented in Rohilkhand plains by government to improve the socio-economic status of Rohilkhands. Most of the researchers have focused upon agriculture and land use in Rohilkhand region his research. A huge gap found in to analysis the socio-economic conditions and in this region. This study tries to examine the level of socio- economic development in different districts of Rohilkhand plains through using weighted index method. The data used to prepare this paper entirely based on secondary sources basically census of India. Through use the weighted index method region has been classified into four parts to assess the comparative analysis of intra-regional disparities across the region. This research paper an attempt has been made to find out the actual socio-economic status of population of different income groups.

Keywords:-

Socio-economic status, Per capita Income, Population, Literacy, Agro-climatic zones

Introduction :-

The contemporary society of developing nations are rapidly moving towards developed economy with the proper social conditions, but these type changes are usually different in every region. In real world, in terms of level of socio-economic development rural areas are comparatively less developed than urban areas. Socio-economic is the most important determinant of the livelihoods as it influences levels of knowledge, skill and income conditions which mean for their living. (Md Monirul Islam, Socio-Economic Status of Rural Population: An Income Level Analysis, 2014) Peoples' way of living is differ from one income group to another as their consumption power is also differ among income groups of population (Mustaquim, M., and Islam, M. (2014)) No region can be developed with the remaining lagging behind. Krieger et al. (1997) define socio-economic position as 'an aggregate concept that includes both resource-based and prestige-based measures, as linked to both childhood and adult social class position.

Rohilkhand plain is one of the most fertile region in Uttar Pradesh Rohilkhand plains may be considered mostly as the plain of Ramganga river which flows its heart of the plain can be further broken by the Tarai, Bhabhar sub-montane belt extending eastward from foothill of shivalik. This region also characterized by very densely populated region in North India.

Rohilkhand region formed by asymmetrical alluvial soil which had filled by Ganga and its tributaries. Rohilkhand plain is doab region between Ramganga and Sarada rivers. This region is highly backward in terms of literacy, education, urbanization, health etc. that's why in this region has lack of sufficient infrastructure. UNDP has been used three indicators viz. per capita income, life expectancy and health to examine the human development in various countries in the world. Per capita income is a dominant factor to examine the socio-economic status of any region. As Rohilkhand plains region has a large amount of densely rural population can also be a cause of slow development. This region is under-developed in human resources and many other aspects

Literature Review:-

Socio-economic status is most emerging issue in contemporary world specially in developing countries. In Indian context it is more vulnerable in across the country. Probably in northern India only few regions are developing in terms of socio-economic parameters. As Mustaquim, M., and Islam, M. (2014) has described Socio-economic characteristics are the important tools to the measures of human development. It is a measure of an individual's or family's or group of people's economic and social position based on education, income, health, and occupation (Mustaquim, M., and Islam, M. (2014)). There is relatively more socio-economic disparity across Rohilkhand plains. Bareilly district is one of the most industrialized district in this region. Rathod & Ningshen (2012), has noted that Socio-economic status is an economic and sociological combined total measure of a person's work experience and of family's economic and social position relative to others, based on income, education, and occupation.

R.L. Singh, 1971 examined that Western part of Rohilkhand plains is relatively more densely populated than eastern part and also relatively more urbanized and industrialized.

Research Objective:-

The Rohilkhand plains is predominantly rural and agrarian. About 72 percent population of the region comes from rural areas. The study throws light on the relationship between the levels of development of agricultural and socio-economic sectors. The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- 1- To examine the level of development of agricultural sector, and overall socio-economic status based on optimum combination of developmental indicators of different district of Rohilkhand plains.
- 2- To assess the regional imbalance between different district of Rohilkhand plains through a comparative study.
- 3- To examine the trending comparative population growth rate in different districts of the Rohilkhand plains.

Study Area:-

The study area Rohilkhand plains is located in north – eastern Uttar Pradesh which is lies between latitudes 27°35' N and 29°58' N and longitudes 78°0' E and 80°27' E (Rahman, 2004). It includes 9 districts *Amroha (Jyotiba phule Nagar), Bareilly, Bijnore, Bandaun, Moradabad, Pilibhit, Rampur, Sambhal , Shahjanpur* of Uttar Pradesh. It has a population of about 28,041,819 with 865 peoples'/km population density. Moradabad district has maximum population and Jyotiba phule Nagar has lowest population in Rohilkhand plains. In other side Moradabad district has highest population density and Pilibhit district has lowest population density (census of India, 2011). Rohilkhand region covers 10.27 percent and 14.05 percentage population of Uttar Pradesh.

Figure-02 : Location of Rohilkhand plains in Uttar Pradesh (source): prepared by author

Rohilkhand plains has a large extent area of about 25000 square kilometers (10000 square miles). It has an extensive area of comparatively level to gently undulating land with lack of surface irregularities and high adjacent area. The average elevation of this region is around 187 meters. It is low land alluvial plain which comes under upper Ganga plain (north). On the east are the low-lying Rohilkhand and Awadh plains. These plains are seamed with deserted rivers. The Ramganga and Sarada rivers meander through the Rohilkhand plains and lower reaches of Gomati and Ghaghara flow through the Awadh plains. On the north, these plains are bordered by the narrow waterless sandy belts of Bhabhar and the swampy belt of alluvial soil (Tarai), supporting vast expanses of marshy land with luxuriant growth of vegetation (N.L. kalara, S.M. kaul, R.M. Rastogi, 1997). According to R.L. Singh (1971) The Upper Ganga plain is the part of the Great Plains lying approximately between the Yamuna in the west covering the parts of Uttarakhand and Uttar Pradesh. The region is delimited in the north by 300m contour which separates it from the Garh - Kum Himalaya west of Sarada while them International boundary of Nepal marks the limit towards the east. In the south the Yamuna demarcates its border with the Bundelkhand. The axis of the topographic trough paradoxically lies nearer the peninsular block or along the Ganga which traverses the area in a south-southeasterly direction. Thus there is, though not perceptible, a tract adjacent to the foot hills where the slope is higher and has resulted in the preponderance of numerous small streams, assigning a somewhat medium to fine texture to this part. The southern counterparts, particularly north of the Ganga are characterized by the sluggish-flowing streams like the Ramganga and the Ghaghara

produced by the changing river courses are predominantly observed in the Ramganga and the Ghaghara valleys, particularly in their flood plains.

Climate:-

The climate of Rohilkhand plains is predominantly monsoon – influenced humid sub-tropical (Cwa – according to Koppen climatic classification); however, weather conditions change significantly with location and season (IMD, 2017). Depending on the elevation, the average temperatures vary from between 12.5-17.50C in January to 27.5-32.50C in May and June (IMD, 2017) Rainfall in the state ranges from between 1,000-2,000 millimeters in the east to 600-1,000 millimeter in the west (IMD, 2017). About 90 percent of the rainfall occurs during the southwest monsoon, lasting from approximately June to September (IMD, 2017). The seasonal reversal of monsoon is the main characteristics of Rohilkhand plains.

Soils:-

Soil is a most crucial factor to determine the agricultural production. Generally, Rohilkhand plains consist of uniform and almost similar characteristics over all the region. On the basis of origin of soils it is mainly developed from deposition of alluvium which has brought by Ganga and its tributaries. These soils can be divided into three parts Bhabhar, Khadar and Bhangar. Bhabhar mainly characterized by mechanically transported alluvium along foothill of Shiwalik and Himalayan range Bhabhar covers upper part of Bijnore district. Khadar is newly alluvium which made by sandy texture with highly fertile soil and Bhangar has characterized by more clay composition.

Database:-

The entire study is based on secondary database which is obtained from different authentic sources and various governmental organizations. In this study three variable have been used viz. per capita income, percentage of literacy and rural population percentage of each district. For per capita income (2018-19) data has been taken from Economics and statistics division, planning department of Uttar Pradesh, statistical diary, 2020. The data of rural population and percentage of literacy have been taken from Census of India factsheet, 2011.

Note – Sambhal (Bhim Nagar) is another district which also comes under Rohilkhand plains but this district has not been included in this study because this district emerged in year 2012 but in this study census of India, 2011 data has been used for literacy and rural population.

Research Methodology :-

Three indicators have been chosen in this study to delineate Rohilkhand plains into sub regions and identify the inter – district disparity in the region which is per capita income rupees, literacy and rural population in percentage. Weighted index method has been used in this study.

DISTRICT	Per C. InLit.	Rur. Pop.	NX1	NX2	NX3	NX1W1	NX2W2	NX3W3	CW	SWI	
BANDAUN	48914	52.91	82.62	0.702	0.866	1.148	0.3512	0.25973	0.22961	0.841	2.52
SHAHJAHAP	61049	61.61	80.3	0.877	1.008	1.116	0.4383	0.30244	0.22316	0.964	2.89
PILIBHIT	66816	63.98	56.02	0.959	1.047	0.778	0.4797	0.31408	0.15568	0.949	2.85
BIJNORE	67796	70.43	74.87	0.974	1.152	1.04	0.4868	0.34574	0.20807	1.041	3.12
MORADABA	69534	58.67	66.98	0.998	0.96	0.931	0.4992	0.28801	0.18614	0.973	2.92
RAMPUR	72163	55.08	74.78	1.036	0.901	1.039	0.5181	0.27039	0.20782	0.996	2.99
BAREILLY	76009	60.52	65	1.091	0.99	0.903	0.5457	0.29709	0.18064	1.023	3.07
AMROHA	94847	65.7	75.16	1.362	1.075	1.044	0.681	0.32252	0.20888	1.212	3.64
AVERAGE	69641	61.113	71.966								3

Table – 01 : Weighted Index Method

Per. C. In. – Per capita Income in INR (2018-19)

Lit. – Literacy in percentage (census, 2011)

Rur. Pop. – Rural Population in percentage (census, 2011)

CWI – Combined Weighted Index

SWI – Single Weighted Index

Table -02 – Assigned weights -

Given Weights	Normalized Given Weight
Per capita income – X1= 50%	0.5
Literacy – X2 = 30%	0.3
Rural Population – X3=20%	0.2

The weights have been given through different variables as per its importance. Table – 02 depicts that 50% weight has been assigned to per capita income because income is most dominant factor for deciding the peoples economic status in particular region, that’s why income considered as a primary variable for this study. 30 percent weight has been assigned to literacy of the districts. then 20% weight has been assigned to rural population of the districts. After assigning the various the normalized weights (NX1, NX2 & NX3) have been computed by dividing the value of the particular district by average of all the districts of that particular variable. After calculating normalized weights (NX1, NX2 & NX3) have been multiplied by normalized given weights (0.5, 0.3, 0.2). After this step we find (NX1W1, NX2W2 & NX3W3) which helps for further computations. This is final weight for the calculation of weights.

After this step, then combined weighted index has been calculated. for calculation of combined weighted index (CWI), final weights of every districts (NX1W1, NX2W2 & NX3W3) added separately and it has been write in separate column, consequently combined weighted index has been calculated by this process.

After that, for calculating combined weighted index of each district, CWI has been divided by number of parameters which is three, to get single weighted index (SWI). For further calculations mean and standard deviation of single weighted index has been calculated for classify the classes into sub - regions. After getting single weighted index values of every districts the single weighted index classified in different classes to using through Mean +- SD (1,2,3.....xn) method which depicts sub - regions of the particular region. Consequently, applying the Sturges rule ($1+3.22 \log N$) for calculating the number of classes, after applying Sturges rule four classes has been emerged.

Region	Class coordinates	Class values	Number of Districts
Region – A	$>(X - 1SD)$	> 2.685	1
Region – B	$(X - 1SD) - X$	2.685 – 3.00	4
Region – C	$X - (X + 1SD)$	3.00 – 3.315	2
Region – D	$(X + 1SD) <$	3.315 <	1

Table – 03: Sub – regions classification on the basis of SWI using (Mean + SD) method

Results:-

After the complete process of calculation, in Rohilkhand plains there are four type sub region has been recognized during this entire study. After the observation of complete data there is huge inter – district disparity in terms of socio - economic status in Rohilkhand plains.

Name of the sub-region	Districts	Socio-economic status
Sub-region - A	Bandaun	Extremely Bad
Sub-region - B	Shahjahanpur, Pilibhit, Moradabad, Rampur	Very Bad
Sub-region - C	Bijnore, Bareilly	Bad
Sub-region - D	Amroha (Jyotiba phule Nagar)	Good

Table -04 : Delineated sub-regions of Rohilkhand plains

In sub – region A has only Bandaun district. Bandaun district has extremely bad performance in terms of socio-economic parameters. Bandaun has very lowest per capita income and literacy rates and having a highest rural population comparison to other districts. In sub-region B have four districts which is Shahjanpur, Pilibhit, Moradabad and Rampur have very bad condition in terms of socio-economic status but better than sub-region A. The sub-region C have two districts named Bijnore and Bareilly. In these two districts Bijnore and Bareilly have bad socio-economic status but it is comparatively better than above all sub-regions. Apart from that sub-region D has only Amroha (Jyotiba phule Nagar) district which has finest socio-economic status among all the districts. Amroha has highest per capita income with good literacy.

After evaluation of complete study of socio-economic status in Rohilkhand plains we have observed that Amroha (Jyotiba phule Nagar) district has a best socio-economic status rest all districts, in another side Bandaun district has lowest performance in terms of socio-economic status. Bijnore and Bareilly districts have an average performance in this study in terms of socio-economic status.

Figure 3 : Sub - Regionalization of Rohilkhand plains on the basis of socio - economic parameters.

Discussion:-

Rohilkhand plains constitutes an important role in economy of Uttar Pradesh. Especially agricultural cereal crops dominate in local economy of this region. Large scale industries viz sugar industries, textile, chemical industries plays major role in the economy of Rohilkhand region. Basically these industries located in urban areas of Moradabad, Bareilly, Pilibhit and Shahjahanpur. Apart from that level of social development is not much sufficient. In this region urbanization rate is very low and literacy rate is another concern about Rohilkhand. The population growth rapidly increasing and in other hand per capita income is remains same.

Basically the sub region A, B and C need to be more focus relatively sub region A. If government will focus upon elementary education, then probably it may be say that per capita income also be increase.

Rohilkhand region covers 14.05 percentage population of Uttar Pradesh. This is a huge percentage of population. In Rohilkhand plains there was a huge change of population trends in last decades (2001-2011).

Serial No.	Districts	Total population (2001)	Total population (2011)	Population growth rate (PGR) %
1	Bareilly	3618589	4448359	22.9
2	Bijnore	3131619	3682713	17.6
3	Bandaun	3069426	3681896	20.0
4	Jyotiba phule Nagar	1499068	1840221	22.8
5	Moradabad	3810983	4772006	25.2
6	Pilibhit	1645183	2031007	23.5
7	Rampur	1923739	2335819	21.4
8	Shahjahanpur	2547855	3006538	18.0

Table – 05: Population trend in Rohilkhand plains.

Figure 4: Population Growth during (2001-2011)

Almost all district has a high amount of population growth rates. Bareilly district has highest population growth among all the districts. In other hand Bijnore district had lowest population growth in last decade. Average growth of population in Rohilkhands about 21.4 percent between 2001-2011 which is very high comparatively normal growth rates.

Figure - 5: Population Growth Rate (%)

Conclusion:-

The broad conclusion emerging from this study is that Rohilkhand plains a very backward region in terms of socio – economic status. only Jyotiba phule Nagar (Amroha) district is a forward region in socio- economic parameters. It means that Jyotiba phule Nagar has a good per capita income, literacy and less rural population which indicates that this district is better than all other districts. Other seven districts viz. Bandaun, Shahjahanpur, Pilibhit, Moradabad, Rampur, Bijnore and Bareilly are backward regions observed in this study that’s why these backward regions needs special attention in terms of enhance the primary education, employment and urban infrastructure. As primary education is more important for every student because students which decide the fortune of any region. Government should need to be more focus on basic infrastructure viz. provide elementary education to every children and employment.

The overall assessment of this study that socio-economic development is positively associated with the infrastructural facilities and literacy rate.

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